

Acknowledgement

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Potential Carcinostats : Synthesis of New

Azo Coumarins*

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COMPOUNDS bearing azo groups are known to exhibit bacterostatic^{1,2} and anticancerous³ activity. Some azo compounds have been reported to inhibit tumor growth in mice and rats⁴. Though vast amount of work has been done on coumarins^{5,6,7}, reference on the synthesis of coumarins using azosalicylaldehydes and malonanilic acids have not come to notice.

In the present investigation 5-phenylazo salicylaldehyde or 5-*m*-toluylazosalicylaldehyde have been condensed with malonanilic acids in absence or presence of trace of piperidine or pyridine and the coumarins(I) and the Schiff bases(II) have been obtained. Maximum yield of the coumarins has been observed when piperidine was used as the condensing agents. Schiff bases were formed in very low yield when piperidine was used as condensing agent. The yield of Schiff base was higher when condensations were done in absence of condensing agents, where the yield of coumarins declined.

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Data concerning new coumarins and Schiff bases are set out in Table 1. Schiff bases were formed in five condensations. Separation of coumarins from Schiff base was done by fractional crystallisation from ethanol, in which the coumarins are very sparingly soluble.

TABLE 1

Compound*	AZO-COUMARINS(I)		Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)
	R	Colour		
1.	H	Darkbrown	17.4	260
2.	CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightbrown	09.2	270(d)
3.	CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Brown	09.2	285(d)
4.	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Brown	09.2	280(d)
5.	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Brown	12.4	320(d)
6.	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Lightbrown	19.05	320(d)
7.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Lightbrown	30.6	320(d)
8.	OCH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightyellow	15.7	290(d)
9.	OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Brown	41.8	305(d)
10.	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Darkbrown	30.4	298(d)
	Schiff bases(II)			
11.	CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Yellow	10.9	111
12.	Cl(<i>o</i>)	Lightbrown	16.0	120
13.	Cl(<i>m</i>)	Lightbrown	07.4	138
14.	Cl(<i>p</i>)	Brown	20.8	131
15.	OCH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Lightyellow	13.00	97

* All compounds analysed well for C, H and N values.

The azo coumarins dyed cotton, silk, wool and polyester fibers in yellow or orange shades, which were fast to light on washing.

Potentiality of the new azo coumarins as carcinostats is currently being assessed.

Experimental

M. ps. are uncorrected. 5-phenylazo salicylaldehyde⁸ and malonanilic acids^{9,10} were prepared by the methods reported in the literature.

Preparations of 5-m-toluylazo salicylaldehyde: *m*-Toluidine (4.5 ml) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (28 ml; 6*M*) and diazotised using sodium nitrite (4 g).

Cold solution of salicylaldehyde (5 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (40 ml; 2*N*) was added slowly with continuous stirring to *m*-toluyl diazonium chloride. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol/acetic acid mixture (1:1), Yield, 6.0 g (62.5%), m.p. 125°.

Found N: 11.30; C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₂ requires N, 11.66%.

Condensations of azo salicylaldehyde with malonanilic acid, formation of 6-(phenylazo) coumarin-3-carboxy anilide: Malonanilic acid (0.900 g; 0.005 mole) and 5-phenyl azosalicylaldehyde (1.30 g; 0.005 mole) were mixed and heated in an oil bath for

ten minutes at 125°, when the mixture first melted, and then set to a dark brown mass. The contents were cooled and digested with sodium-bicarbonate solution and washed with water. The Schiff base was removed by extraction with hot ethanol (15 ml) and the residue was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, when 6-(phenylazo) coumarin-3-carboxyanilide was obtained as dark brown crystals, m.p. 260° (d), Yield, 0.38 g (17.4%); Found N : 11.2; $C_{22}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires N : 11.38%.

The filtrate was concentrated when crystals of 2-hydroxy-*p*-(phenylazo) benzyldene aniline separated out.

The aforementioned procedure is illustrative of the method used for the preparation of coumarins and Schiff bases listed in Table 1.

Ir of coumarin (I.R= OCH_3) in KBr pellets shows vibrational frequencies at 1685 cm^{-1} due to C=O stretching, at 1555 cm^{-1} due to azo stretching, frequency at 1710 cm^{-1} shows the presence of coumarin ring and at 1350 cm^{-1} due to $-CH_3$ group.

N.m.r. ($CDCl_3$; T.M.S. standard) shows signals at τ 7.8 (3H, CH_3); τ 2.8 (4H, C_6H_4) and τ 3.1 (3H, C_6H_5).

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